

IMPACT OF HANDEDNESS ON PROBLEM SOLVING SKILLS PERFORMANCE AND ATTITUDES AMONG JUNIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Impact of Handedness on Problem Solving Skills Performance and Attitudes among Junior High School Students

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Abstract

Students' learning can be affected by different factors. One of these factors that is linked to how students acquire knowledge is their hand preference, widely known as handedness. This interconnection between handedness and brain lateralization shoots a tiny spark of thought to its influence on learning. This study determines the impact of handedness on the problem-solving skills and performance of junior high school students at Pilot Provincial Science and Technology High School. The test survey questionnaire for attitude towards problem-solving, the test questionnaire for problem-solving skills performance, and the test for handedness are the instruments of this study. The data are composed of the student's mean ratings in their attitude and mean scores for the test questionnaire on problem-solving. Descriptive statistics showed that the problem-solving skills performance of the right-handed and left-handed students in terms of understanding the problem, making a plan, carrying out the plan, and looking back are found satisfactory as shown by the mean 22.03 and 22.91, respectively, and this means both are proficient in solving Math problems. In addition, the mean ratings on the attitude towards problem-solving of both the right- and the left-handed students yielded positive results, and all showed "agree" in cognitive, psychomotor, and affective domains, as revealed by the mean values 3.145 and 3.115, respectively. This implies that both right- and left-handed students show positive attitudes toward problem-solving. It was shown that there is a significant relationship between the skills performance and attitude toward problem-solving of right-handed students ($r=0.535$, $p=0.008$). Further, there is a moderately significant relationship that exists between the skills performance of left-handed students and their attitude toward problem-solving ($r=0.625$, $p=0.0002$). It was also determined that there is no substantial evidence to show that the difference between the mean scores in problem-solving skills between the right- and left-handed students is significant ($t=-0.558$, $df=19$). Finally, there was no significant difference between the mean ratings in the attitude towards problem-solving of the right- and left-handed students ($t=0.656$, $df=19$).

Keywords: *handedness, problem solving skills performance, attitudes, junior high school students*

Introduction

Students' learning can be affected by different factors. One of these factors that linked on how students acquire knowledge is their hand preference, widely known as handedness. This interconnection between handedness and brain lateralization shoots a tiny spark of thought to its influence in learning (Vijayan et al., 2017). Handedness is the dominance of one hand over the other, or the unequal distribution of fine motor skills between the left and right hands. It refers to the tendency of humans to be more dexterous or skilled with one hand over the other, or sometimes merely the preference of one hand over the other. It is usually used with reference to fine motor skills and the performance of manual tasks, particularly everyday activities such as writing or throwing (Mastin, 2012). With this definition, it can be implied that students could be either left-handed, right-handed or both-handed.

Mastin (2012) further added that there are four types of handedness. He mentioned right-handedness (dextrality) where people are more dexterous with, or primarily use, their right hand when performing manual tasks, left-handedness (or sinistrality) where people are more dexterous with, or primarily use, their left hand when performing manual tasks, mixed-handedness (or cross-dominance) where people tend to perform different tasks better with different hands and ambidexterity where people are able to perform any task equally well with either hand. According to psychology, learning is affected by these hand preferences due to factors such as ability and brain functions. Handedness is a manifestation of the lateralization of human brain function, and consequently, hand preference is believed to affect human overall cognitive skills (McManus, 2019). However, in spite of much research carried out on this topic, the shape of this relationship is still highly controversial.

Some researchers claim that the hand-preference or the dominance of the right or the left hand has something to do with mathematical ability and affects how students deal with math problems. The effect of handedness on mathematical ability have been a matter of interest (Cheyne et al., 2010). It has been believed that left-handed people has the greater tendency to be more proficient in Mathematics compared to its other counterpart. According to Sala and Gobet (2017), left-handers exhibit, on average, a more developed right brain hemisphere, which is specialized for processes such as spatial reasoning and the ability to rotate mental representations of objects. Scholars claimed that left-handedness is not related to any advantage in cognitive skills, and may even exert detrimental effects on general cognitive function and, hence, academic achievement. Johnston et al. (2009) revealed that left-handed children slightly underperformed in a series of developmental measures. Left-handers were over-represented among intellectually challenged individuals and did slightly worse in spatial ability tasks, respectively (Papadatou-Pastou & Tomprou, 2015).

A learners' hand preference can also affect the problem-solving ability since it has something to do with the functions of the brain.

Problem solving is a fundamental means of developing mathematical knowledge at any level. Since one of the timeless trends in the educational system is the identification of Mathematical ability, the researcher is interested to investigate the problem-solving attitude and skills of Junior High School Students of Pilot Provincial Science and Technology High School. Particularly, it aims to find out if there is a significant relationship between the problem-solving attitude and skills and handedness of junior high school students of Pilot Provincial Science and Technology High School.

Research Questions

The study was primarily conducted to investigate the problem-solving attitude and skills of left and right-handed Junior High School students. Specifically, it aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What is the skills performance on problem-solving of the right-and left- handed junior high school students in terms of:
 - 1.1. understanding the problem;
 - 1.2. making a plan;
 - 1.3. carrying out the plan; and
 - 1.4. looking back?
2. What is the attitude towards problem-solving of the right and left-handed junior high school students in terms of:
 - 2.1. cognitive;
 - 2.2. psychomotor; and
 - 2.3. affective
3. Is there a significant relationship between the skills performance and attitude on problem solving of right- handed students?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the skills performance and attitude on problem solving of left – handed students?
5. Is there a significant difference in the skills performance in problem solving of right- and left – handed students?
6. Is there a significant difference in the attitude towards problem-solving of right- and left– handed students?

Methodology

Research Design

This study made use descriptive-correlational design of study. A descriptive correlational study is a study in which the researcher is primarily interested in describing relationships among variables, without seeking to establish a causal connection. The descriptive part utilized a survey to identify the attitude towards problem -solving and a test questionnaire used to identify the problem-solving skills of the students. The correlation between the variables such as the handedness and problem-solving attitude and skills was established.

Respondents

The respondents of the study were composed of 40 junior high school students of Pilot Provincial Science and Technology High School. They were chosen from each grade level and were officially enrolled students of school year 2019-2020. Each grade level was composed of five (5) right-handed students and so as with left-handed.

Instruments

The researcher used an adapted and modified survey questionnaire, test questionnaire and a test for handedness to gather data in the study. The survey questionnaire measured the attitude and the test questionnaire was used to identify the problem-solving skills.

The survey questionnaire was composed of thirty (30) questions that describe the attitude towards problem-solving of the students. It was divided into three (3) sections of attitude such as cognitive, psychomotor and affective.

The test questionnaire was composed of ten (10) word problems divided into five categories: number, age, fraction, money and rate problems. Each category was composed of two-word problem questions. The word problems covered three out of six of the Revised Bloom's Taxonomy level of cognitive learning namely: remembering, understanding and applying.

A test for handedness called the Edinburgh Handedness inventory was adapted to assess the dominance of the students' right or left hand in everyday activities. The inventory is composed of fifteen checklists for each activity. A laterality index interpreted the right- or left-handedness of the respondents. This was administered for 1 and a half (1 ½) hour to maximize the answering time.

The researcher made use of the Cronbach Alpha to measure the reliability of the instrument and obtained a value of .847 which means the instrument is reliable. The study used content validity to ensure that the instrument is valid and obtained a mean of 3.945 interpreted as agree which means that instrument is valid.

Procedure

After the instrument will be validated, the researcher sought permission in the office of the Schools Division Superintendent of Cotabato City and the principal of the school to conduct the study. A letter of permission indicating the purpose of the survey was secured. The instruments were distributed to the respondents and were given one and a half (1 ½) hour to answer the questionnaire. The data gathered from this research were tallied and computed for interpretation according to the responses. Along with primary data, the researcher will

make us of secondary sources to support survey results.

Data Analysis

After collecting the data, attitude and problem-solving skills of the respondents, the researcher used the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) in analyzing the students' responses.

Measures of central tendency and variability were used to interpret the responses on the survey questionnaire and test for problem-solving skills and the Pearson correlation coefficient or the bivariate correlation, measured the linear correlation between the two variables, problem solving attitude and problem-solving skills. The t-test for independent samples was also used to compare the means between left- and right-handed students. The results of the Edinburgh Handedness Inventory were analyzed using an online laterality computation and interpreted using the laterality index.

Results and Discussion

This section represents gathered data, statistical analysis results and the interpretation of each finding. The results aim to determine the skills performance and attitude towards problem-solving, the relationship between the skills performance and attitude towards problem solving of both the left and right-handed students and the significant difference between the skills performance and attitude toward problem solving of the left and right-handed students.

Problem Solving Skills Performance of Right-Handed Students

This shows the skills of right-handed students in problem solving in terms of understanding the problem, making a plan, carrying out the plan and looking back.

Table 1. Mean Scores on the Problem-Solving Performance Skills of Right- Handed Students

Skills in Problem-Solving	Mean	SD	Description
Understanding the Problem	23.10	5.004	Satisfactory
Making a Plan	27.00	5.140	Very Satisfactory
Carrying out the Plan	23.35	4.392	Satisfactory
Looking Back	14.65	3.689	Fairly Satisfactory
Overall Mean	22.03	4.556	Satisfactory

Note: 33-40, Outstanding; 25-32, Very Satisfactory; 17-24, Satisfactory; 9-26, Fairly Satisfactory; 0-8, Did Not Meet Expectation

Based on Table 1 on the next page, the process of Looking Back got the lowest mean of 14.65 which indicates "Fairly Satisfactory". Understanding the problem and Carrying out the Plan are both "Satisfactory" with the mean scores of 23.10 and 23.35 respectively. Further, Making a Plan is Very Satisfactory with the mean value of 27.00. As a whole, right-handed students have "Satisfactory" rating as indicated by the over-all mean score of 22.03 and standard deviation of 4.556. This indicates that right-handed students are generally competent when it comes to problem-solving and are inclined in finding solutions rather than checking the process.

Right-handed with no familial left-handedness are hypothesized to be highly lateralized for certain types of problem-solving and invariably do better in handling verbal material within the left-hemisphere (Elsevier, 2020).

Problem Solving Skills Performance of Left-Handed Students

Table 2. Mean Scores of Problem-Solving Performance Skills of Left-Handed

Skills in Problem-Solving	Mean	SD	Description
Understanding the Problem	24.95	8.971	Satisfactory
Making a Plan	25.30	7.420	Very Satisfactory
Carrying out the Plan	24.10	9.002	Very Satisfactory
Looking Back	17.30	5.079	Fairly Satisfactory
Overall Mean	22.91	7.618	Satisfactory

Note: 33-40, Outstanding; 25-32, Very Satisfactory; 17-24, Satisfactory; 9-26, Fairly Satisfactory; 0-8, Did Not Meet Expectation

An illustration of the left-handed students' problem-solving performance skill will be shown below described with the following process such as understanding the problem, making a plan, carrying out the plan and looking back.

It is indicated in Table 2 in the next page that the left handed students are “Fairly Satisfactory” in Looking Back as reflected by the mean of 17.30. Moreover, Understanding the Problem (24.95) and Carrying out the Plan (24.10) are rated “Satisfactory”. Finally, Looking Back is “Very Satisfactory” with mean rating of 25.30. Generally, left-handed students performed satisfactorily in problem solving as shown by the overall mean score of 22.91. It can be implied that lefties are competent in problem solving but needs improvement in looking back to their solution.

This is inclined with the findings of Lore (2017) where left-handers were found to exhibit a more developed right brain hemisphere which specializes in processes such as spatial reasoning and the ability to visualize mental representations of objects.

Attitude of Right-Handed Students towards Problem Solving

Cognitive, psychomotor and affective domain are used to identify right- handed students’ attitude towards problem solving.

Table 3. Mean Ratings of Attitude of Right-Handed Students towards Problem Solving

Domain of Learning	Mean	SD	Description
Cognitive	3.27	0.443	Agree
Psychomotor	3.00	0.521	Agree
Affective	3.18	0.450	Agree
Overall Mean	3.15	0.424	Agree

Note: 3.50-4.00, Strongly Agree; 2.50-3.49, Agree; 1.50-2.49, Disagree; 1.00-1.49, Strongly Disagree

Table 3 suggests that attitude of right-handed students under the three domains of learning such as cognitive (3.27), affective (3.18) and psychomotor (3.00) exhibited positive attitude towards problem solving as indicated by the rating of “Agree”. It is further justified that, in general, the students have good attitude as revealed by the overall mean 3.15.

Right handers have genes that force their brain into a slightly one-sided structure which is needed to understand systematically tasks on problem solving. This process in the brain enables them to be motivated in handling task such as problem solving (Ghayas and Adil, 2007).

Attitude of Left-Handed Students towards Problem Solving

The following variables such as cognitive, psychomotor and affective domains are used to determine left-handed students’ attitude towards problem solving.

Table 4. Mean Ratings of Attitude of Left-Handed Students towards Problem Solving

Domain of Learning	Mean	SD	Description
Cognitive	3.26	0.448	Agree
Psychomotor	2.99	0.421	Agree
Affective	3.10	0.445	Agree
Overall Mean	3.12	0.438	Agree

Note: 3.50-4.00, Strongly Agree; 2.50-3.49, Agree; 1.50-2.49, Disagree; 1.00-1.49, Strongly Disagree

It is clearly stated in Table 4 that the attitude of the left-handed students are all rated as “Agree” under the three domains such as cognitive (3.26), affective (3.10) and psychomotor (2.99). The results manifest a desirable attitude as further indicated by the overall mean of 3.12. Thus, it can be inferred that left-handed students are driven to solve math problems.

Left-handers, motivation was associated with greater activity in the left hemisphere of the brain. It implies that motivation is important attitude to problem solving (Plos ONE, 2012).

Relationship between Right-Handed Students Attitude and Problem Solving Skills Performance

The relationship between the right-handed students’ attitude and problem- solving performance skills will be shown as indicated by the Pearson’s r value.

Table 5. Pearson’s r Results between Right-Handed Students’ Attitude and Performance Skill in Problem Solving

Variables	Pearson’s r	p-value	Interpretation
Attitude			
Performance Skills	0.535	0.008	Significant

*Correlation is significant at .05 level (1-tailed)

The above results revealed that there a significant relationship between the skills performance and attitude on problem solving of left-handed students ($r=0.535$). It further emphasizes that moderate correlation exists between the two variables, thus, the hypothesis “There is no significant relationship between the skills performance and attitude on problem solving of right – handed students” is rejected. It implies that a positive attitude among the students towards problem solving yields a good performance skill.

Attitudes had made a significant contribution to mathematical problem solving and mathematics achievement (Mohd and Mahmood, 2011).

Relationship between Left-Handed Students Attitude and Problem-Solving Skills Performance

Relationship with left-handed students’ attitude ad performance skills will be established as revealed by the Pearson’s r value below.

Table 6. *Pearson’s r Results between Left-Handed Students’ Attitude and Performance Skill in Problem Solving*

Variables	Pearson’s r	p-value	Interpretation
Attitude	0.625	0.002	Significant
Performance Skills			

**Correlation is significant at .05 level (1-tailed)*

An inspection of Table 6 clarifies that there a significant relationship between the skills performance and attitude on problem solving of left-handed students ($r=0.625$). It further emphasizes that moderate correlation exists between the two variables. Therefore, the hypothesis of “There is no significant relationship between the skills performance and attitude on problem solving of left – handed students” is rejected. It can be inferred from the above results that high performance results from a desirable attitude in problem solving. The statement above agrees with McManus (2002) statement that says left- handers have improved power of perception and are creative, likely to notice size, shape and form of things and are more likely to see the whole picture or concept.

Difference between Right- and Left-handed Skills Performance in Problem Solving

Significant difference between the right-and left-handed students’ performance skills in problem solving are shown below as revealed by the t-value.

Table 7. *T- Test Results between Right- and Left-handed Students Performance Skills in Problem-Solving*

Variables	Mean	df	t-value	p-value	Interpretation
Right-handed	81.10	19	-0.558	.584	Not significant
Left-handed	91.65				

**Correlation is significant at .05 level (1-tailed)*

It is observed in Table 7 that there is no significant difference between the right- and left-handed students’ performance skills in problem solving ($t=-0.558$, $df=19$). Hence, null hypothesis “There is no significant difference in the skills performance in problem solving of left- and right -handed students.” is accepted. This further emphasizes that handedness does not affect the problem solving-skills performance of both the right and left-handed students, even though left-handed students got a slightly higher mean. This is true with Sala and Gobet (2017) findings that when the task is not too demanding, such as when doing simple arithmetic, there was no significant difference between left- and right handers. However, the findings of Ghayas and Adil (2007) is contradictory to the findings where it states that left-handers are creative and are significantly more intelligent than right-handers.

Difference between Right- and Left-handed Attitudes towards Problem Solving

The table below identifies the significant difference between the attitude of right-and left-handed students towards problem-solving.

Table 8. *T- Test Results between Right- and Left-handed Students Attitude towards Problem-Solving*

Variables	Mean	df	t-value	p-value	Interpretation
Right-handed	3.145	19	0.453	0.656	Not significant
Left-handed	3.115				

**Correlation is significant at .05 level (1-tailed)*

Table 8 results indicates that there is no significant difference between the right- and left-handed students' attitude towards problem solving ($t=0.656$, $df=19$). Hence, null hypothesis "There is no significant difference in the attitude towards problem solving of right- and left – handed students." is accepted. The result confirms handedness does not affect the problem attitude towards problem solving of both the right and left-handed students.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, attitude affects skills performance of students in solving mathematical problems. Positive attitude drives them to be more efficient in finding solutions to problem. In addition, handedness is not a factor to determine desirable attitude and performance of students.

Based on the findings and conclusion of the study, the following recommendations are suggested: Teachers must incorporate different strategies in teacher problem so that does not discriminate both the right- and left-handed students. Teachers must utilize motivational activities to boost student's interest in Solving Math problems. School administrators must provide facilities and equipment such as chair and other materials that are appropriate for left-handers. The researcher must study in the future other related on handedness and problem solving such as the age, gender and nature of the problem. Future researchers should broaden the study on the effect of handedness on the Intelligence Quotient of the students.

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